

Delay Analysis Methods in Construction Projects: Applications and Practical Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Delay analysis in the construction industry is critical yet complex, often leading to disputes among project stakeholders due to the variety of available methodologies and their varying degrees of applicability and reliability. This work explores the terminology commonly used in the context of construction project delays and evaluates widely accepted delay analysis methods. The evaluation highlights the strengths and weaknesses of each method, as well as the practical challenges associated with their implementation. The purpose of this work is to provide stakeholders with clear guidance on the appropriate selection and application of these methods, thereby fostering more effective and accurate dispute resolution within the construction industry. This work is intended as a practitioner oriented technical guide.

Keywords: Delay analysis, construction delays, dispute resolution, baseline schedule, critical path, extension of time

1. INTRODUCTION

The assessment and analysis of delay related claims in the construction industry has long been a source of significant contention and disagreement among construction project stakeholders. Delay and disruption matters evolve into disputes on many occasions [1]. Disputes between the Employer and Contractor often arise not only over the complexities of the project itself but also over fundamental definitions, interpretations of contract clauses, and the respective rights of each party. Resolution of the delay-related disputes is central to accurately determining and assigning responsibility between the claiming and defending parties [2]. Researchers and practitioners have adopted number of delay analysis methods over time [3]. The diversity in the methods employed to evaluate delays can further complicate the process, as the effectiveness and reliability of each methodology can vary depending on the project's nature, size, value, the practitioner's skill level, scope, and contractual framework [4].

This study aims to explore the terminology commonly used within the construction industry regarding project delays, examine the various delay analysis methodologies that have gained wide acceptance, and critically evaluate their applicability, reliability, and validity. Drawing from both established literature and insights gained through extensive professional practice, this work provides a balanced overview of the tools and techniques available for delay analysis in construction projects, while also addressing common misunderstandings and challenges faced by practitioners. By offering a comprehensive understanding of these methodologies, this study seeks to provide valuable insights to stakeholders involved in delay related disputes.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 BASIC DEFINITIONS

Baseline Schedule

A Baseline Schedule (BS), is the original, ideally approved/acknowledged by the Employer project timeline that serves as a reference point for tracking project performance over time. It includes the planned start and finish dates for all activities, key milestones, and the critical path. Once established, BS is considered as the commencement point of most forensic schedule analyses [5], and becomes the benchmark against which actual progress, delays, and deviations are measured throughout the project lifecycle. It constitutes the essential foundation upon which most of the delay analyses are built and entitlements to claims are evaluated.

Delay

A delay refers to a deviation from the original timeline, resulting in the postponement of planned activity, activities and/or the overall project completion. Delay in construction contracts is described as the difference between the intention (i.e. contractually binding completion date or the Contractor's planned programme for the work) and reality as to the timing of the work where the reality is in derogation from the intention [6]. Delay is acknowledged as the most common, costly, complex, and risky problem in construction projects [7].

Without implying any order of significance, construction delays may stem from various factors, including but not limited to design modifications during construction, late site handover, inadequate contractor experience, ineffective planning and supervision, belated payment processes, unreliable subcontractors, late material deliveries, adverse weather conditions, and lack of communication and coordination [8].

Critical Path

The longest path from commencement to project completion irrespective of the constraints in the schedule represents the critical path (CP) [6]. Any delay to an activity on the CP directly affects the project completion date, making it a focal point in delay analysis.

Extension of Time:

In construction projects, Extension of Time (EOT) is an official adjustment to the project's completion date, granted to the Contractor when delays occur due to events that are beyond the control of and not attributable to the Contractor. The Contractor's EOT claim submission should ideally be substantiated and supported by detailed records and delay analysis demonstrating links between the delaying events and their impact on the project's completion. The records, that need to be kept regularly and constantly, should identify what happened, when they occurred, what their impacts were on activities and on completion as a whole [9].

Total Float

Total float is described as time by which an activity may be delayed or extended without affecting the total project duration [10]. It is a key parameter in assessing delay analyses and frequently emerges as a point of contention among project stakeholders.

In many construction contracts, the ownership of float is not explicitly defined. The absence of clearly defined contractual provisions regarding float ownership and the treatment of concurrent delays often becomes a source of dispute in delay analysis and time-related claims. In such cases, the prevailing industry practice is to treat float as a commodity to the project [11] and to consider it available to either party on a first-come, first-served basis [12].

Concurrent Delay

Concurrent delays are described as two or more delays occur simultaneously and independently, each attributable to different parties or causes, and each affecting the project's CP [13]. The allocation of responsibility in such cases remains a contentious issue in both practice and legal adjudication [14].

Disruption

Disruptions are described as events that prevent the contractor completing the work as planned [15]. Disruptions impair the Contractor's ability to perform its work efficiently, without necessarily causing a delay to the overall project completion and they often lead to reduced productivity, increased costs, and claims for additional compensation.

Excusable Delay

Excusable delays are the ones that are typically caused by events beyond the control of and not attributable to the Contractor [16], such as force majeure, unforeseeable site conditions, or delays caused by the Employer. These delays may entitle the Contractor to a time extension, but not necessarily to additional compensation.

Non-Excusable Delay

A non-excusable delay is a delay for which the Contractor is solely responsible [17], typically resulting from issues such as inadequate planning, labor issues, or failure to procure materials on time. Such delays generally do not warrant any relief to the Contractor and may lead to liquidated damages and/or other contractual penalties.

Compensable Delay

Compensable delay is described as a period of time during a critical delay event is experienced which is the Employer's risk event [18]. In such cases, the Contractor may be entitled to both a time extension and monetary compensation to recover incurred costs.

Non-Compensable Delay

A non-compensable delay is an excusable delay where the Contractor is granted additional time, but no additional costs are provided. These delays often result from force majeure events or other circumstances that are contractually identified as non-compensable.

Culpable Delay

Culpable delay is an expression used to describe the Contractor's delay [1].

Fragnet

A fragnet (also known as a sub-network) is a small fragment of a schedule, prepared to depict the impact of a delay event [19]. As part of delay analysis, fragnets are inserted into the BS to simulate and evaluate the potential effects of delay events on the overall project timeline by assessing how specific delays might affect the project's CP and completion date.

2.2 The Importance of BS and Project Records

In construction projects, the BS's which are formally approved/recognized by the Employer constitutes the contractual foundation for monitoring progress and evaluating potential delays. It serves as a central reference throughout the project lifecycle and forms the basis for assessing entitlement to EOT. As construction progresses, it becomes essential to regularly update the baseline schedule to reflect actual site conditions, progress, and

resource allocations. These updated CPM programmes serve not only to capture the project's evolving status but also to provide a transparent and contemporaneous record that helps in identifying and assessing the causes and impacts of disruptive events. Updated schedules offer a more accurate basis for both contemporaneous, forensic delay analyses, supporting effective communication, documentation, and dispute resolution processes [20].

While the BS remains a key reference, it is important to recognize that by its' nature, the project's CP is dynamic and it may change as the project progresses; it adjusts in response to actual execution on site and the timing of emerging events. Accordingly, delay assessments based solely on the original BS may not fully represent the practical circumstances unless supported by regular updates. Delay analysis is typically conducted through a comparative assessment of the as-planned and as-built schedules [21]. The comparison of an impacted schedule, reflecting the timing and consequences of delay events, with the originally approved/recognized BS offers a more accurate and credible basis for substantiating time-related claims.

Maintaining a clear record of updated schedules throughout the course of the works not only supports effective project control but also facilitates the preparation of defensible EOT submissions. Such documentation helps demonstrate cause-and-effect relationships in a manner that is generally regarded as reliable by dispute resolution boards, courts, and other relevant authorities.

A robust and credible delay analysis fundamentally depends on the availability, accuracy, and timeliness of contemporaneous project records. Documents such as daily site reports, progress meeting minutes, certified payment applications, delivery and inspection logs, photographs, regularly updated project schedules and cost reports constitute the evidentiary foundation upon which retrospective delay evaluations are built [4]. These records not only reflect the actual progress and conditions encountered on site, but also provide a factual timeline against which the impact of delaying events may be measured with precision.

In the absence of such documentation, or where records are incomplete, inconsistent, or poorly maintained, the reliability and persuasiveness of the delay assessment are significantly compromised. If the analysis is not supported by concrete and verifiable facts, it may be regarded as speculative and unreliable, thereby reducing its credibility and weight in dispute resolution proceedings or legal forums. Therefore, maintaining systematic and well-organized project records is not merely good practice but a procedural safeguard that enhances the defensibility of any EOT claim.

Moreover, the accurate identification and classification of delay events are critical to determining responsibility and entitlement. Distinguishing between critical and non-critical delays, excusable and non-excusable events, as well as compensable and non-compensable impacts, is a fundamental aspect of delay analysis. These classifications must be supported by objective, verifiable evidence derived from the project's historical records and, when applicable, be aligned with the explicit provisions of the governing contract. Failure to apply these distinctions accurately may lead to flawed conclusions and, in some cases, result in the dismissal of the claim.

2.3 Delay Analysis Methods

There is a wide range of methods and techniques are utilized to analyze project delays in the construction industry. These methods vary in complexity and application, depending on the nature of the project, the available data, and the specific requirements of the delay analysis. Among these, there are several approaches that are widely recognized and frequently used by professionals for assessing delays and their impact on project schedules. The five most commonly used delay analysis methods in the industry are: Impacted As-Planned, As-Planned vs. As-Built, Collapsed As-Built, Windows Analysis, and Time Impact Analysis [22].

2.3.1 Impacted As-Planned

Definition

Impacted As-Planned (IAP) is a static method that involves inserting hypothetical delay events (fragnets) into the original BS. These hypothetical events are used to evaluate the potential impact of delays on the project's completion date [23]. The BS remains unchanged, and the delays are analyzed based on the assumption of how they would have affected the project timeline if they had occurred. This method is typically used where actual as-built data is unavailable or incomplete, small to medium-scale projects that have a relatively simple scheduling structure, projects lacking detailed progress updates or actual performance data. Since this method does not reflect actual project developments, relies on an as-planned schedule and fails to incorporate delay events caused by all parties concurrently, it has been subject to considerable criticism for its lack of accuracy and reliability [3].

Advantages

Simple and straightforward to implement.

Effective for analyzing theoretical delays in early-stage projects.

Does not require actual progress data or complex updates to the schedule.

Disadvantages

Lacks consideration of actual project performance and progress.

Potentially speculative, as it does not reflect actual events or performance.

Limited applicability for complex projects or those with concurrent delays.

2.3.2 As-Planned vs. As-Built

Definition

The As-Planned vs. As-Built (APAB) method compares the BS with the actual schedule, evaluating the differences between what was intended (planned) and what was actually accomplished (as-built) [24]. While the APAB is a static method, any new activities identified in the as-built schedule can be modeled as delays [25]. The APAB method is generally considered effective in projects where the actual progress closely aligns with the BS, however, its applicability may be more limited in large-scale or highly complex projects with multiple or evolving CPs.

Advantages

Easy to understand and implement.

Based on the actual CP of the project.

Simple to perform.

Disadvantages

Less effective for projects that deviated significantly from the original plan

May not perform well with projects that have multiple CPs.

2.3.3 Collapsed As-Built

Definition

The Collapsed As-Built (CAB) method, also known as "But-For Analysis" is a retrospective delay analysis technique that simulates the project's schedule by removing specific delay events (such as owner-caused delays) from the as-built schedule [26]. This method essentially reconstructs a hypothetical "what-if" scenario to determine the project's completion date had the delays not occurred. CAB is a static method and relies heavily on the integrity of the as-built data.

Advantages

Easy to understand.

Utilizes as-built records reflecting real progress, durations, and sequences, increasing reliability.

Isolates specific delay impacts and allows the effect of individual delay therefore helps distinguish between Contractor and Employer delays by hypothetically removing one party's delays.

Disadvantages

Subjective in the selection of delay events to collapse, which may lead to disputes.

May oversimplify complex delay interactions.

Requires well-maintained and accurate as-built schedules, which may not always be available.

If delay removals or logic changes are not properly justified or documented, the analysis may lack objectivity.

2.3.4 Windows Analysis

Definition

Windows Analysis (WA) divides the project timeline into "windows" or smaller periods, where delay events are analyzed within each window based on updated schedules [27]. Each window is treated as a separate analysis period, allowing for detailed evaluation of delays over time and their impact on the overall project. This method is typically used in large and complex projects with multiple delay events occurring over different periods, projects where detailed as-built and updated schedule data is available, forensic or retrospective analysis to understand how delays occurred across different phases of the project. WA is a dynamic method, as it incorporates updates in project progress and considers the timeline impact of delays in distinct periods.

Advantages

Highly detailed and accurate, allowing for an in-depth understanding of delays over time.

Can account for concurrent delays, re-sequencing, and mitigation efforts.

Useful for analyzing complex projects with numerous interdependencies and delay events.

Disadvantages

Requires regular and accurate schedule updates, making it time-consuming and costly to implement.

Can be difficult to manage and interpret for large projects with numerous delays and factors.

Data-heavy, requiring comprehensive project records and resources for effective analysis.

2.3.5 Time Impact Analysis

Definition

Time Impact Analysis (TIA), which is also considered as a variant of WA, is a dynamic method that involves inserting delay events into updated project schedules to assess the impact of each event on the CP and overall project duration [4]. This method allows for the evaluation of delays based on real-time project data, including current progress and updated schedule information. TIA is typically used in large-scale, ongoing projects, where delay events are actively monitored and adjusted over time, projects with frequent updates and progress status reports, complex projects with multiple delay events that need to be evaluated in real-time. This is a dynamic method, as it takes actual progress and updated data into consideration, making it more accurate for ongoing or complex projects.

Advantages

Provides a dynamic and accurate reflection of how delays affect the CP.

Can demonstrate cause-effect relationships and their impact on the project completion date.

Allows for the inclusion of mitigation efforts and re-sequencing of tasks.

Disadvantages

Requires frequent and detailed schedule updates, making it time-consuming and costly.

Highly data-intensive and resource-heavy, requiring robust project management software.

Complex to explain and interpret for stakeholders without technical expertise.

2.4 Selection of the Appropriate Delay Analysis Method

The selection of an appropriate delay analysis methodology is crucial for accurately determining the cause and impact of delays in construction projects. There is no one single solution applicable to all cases when it comes to choosing the right delay analysis method [3]. The selected method should align with the specific circumstances of the project, such as the availability of contemporaneous records, the complexity of the delays, and the resources (both financial and time-related) available for the analysis. The reliability of delay analysis is influenced not only by the selected methodology, but also by several factors such as the treatment of concurrent delays, the allocation of float, the approach adopted for identifying the critical path, and the scheduling techniques employed [28]. Each delay analysis method offers distinct advantages and limitations, and the decision to choose one over another should be driven by multiple factors, including the project's unique requirements and the available documentation.

Not to mention, the expertise, skill level, and professional judgment of the individual conducting the analysis can significantly influence the overall quality, coherence, and acceptability of the results [4]. A delay analysis method, even when technically sound and contractually appropriate, may yield limited or contested conclusions if not applied with sufficient methodological rigor and contextual awareness. Therefore, the analyst's familiarity with the selected approach, their ability to interpret project data objectively, and their understanding of scheduling principles are all critical to producing a credible and defensible analysis.

As a preliminary step in the selection process, it is essential to first examine whether the contract includes a clause explicitly specifying the delay analysis methodology to be used in the event of time-related disputes. If such a provision exists, it should be followed, as contractual terms take precedence over general industry practice.

WA and TIA are widely regarded as the most reliable and accepted delay analysis methodologies in the industry. These methods are particularly useful when there are sufficient time and financial resources to perform a detailed and comprehensive analysis. Both methodologies are well-documented, highly transparent, and commonly accepted in legal and dispute resolution settings due to their detailed nature and the fact that they rely on primary data sources, making them highly persuasive when presenting evidence in disputes. WA is generally preferred when a broader, period-by-period evaluation is sufficient to understand the overall delay trends, and when efficiency and cost-effectiveness are priorities. It allows the analyst to examine how delays affected the project over successive intervals using updated schedules. TIA, by contrast, focuses on modeling the impact of each delay event individually by inserting it into the schedule at the point it occurred. Although this approach can offer greater precision and clarity, it typically requires more time and resources. In practice, WA may be more suitable when a quicker yet reliable overview is needed, whereas TIA is often the method of choice for high-value, complex, or legally sensitive claims that demand detailed event-level analysis.

When resources or time constraints limit the ability to apply more sophisticated methods like TIA or WA, the APAB method becomes a practical alternative. This method involves comparing the original, approved/recognized BS with the actual progress (as-built). It is a useful way to evaluate the differences between planned and actual progress. This approach is particularly suitable when time and financial constraints restrict the ability to implement more complex analyses. Its simplicity makes it an attractive choice in situations where a quick, cost-effective analysis is needed, and/or the project documentation may be limited or not as detailed.

For certain projects with straightforward delay events and minimal complexity, the CAB method can offer an effective means of analysis. This method involves adjusting the project schedule backward by "collapsing" non-impacted portions of the schedule to reflect delays. It is particularly useful in scenarios where delays can be isolated to specific activities, and the impact is clear and well-defined. However, this method has limitations when it comes to projects with concurrent or overlapping delays, as it may not fully account for the interplay between multiple delay events. Therefore, its applicability is more suited to projects where delay events are discrete and can be analyzed in isolation.

In cases where As-Built data is unavailable, incomplete and/or it is not feasible to create it retrospectively, the IAP method can be used as a last resort. This methodology applies delay events to the original BS (As-Planned), without utilizing any actual progress data. While this method can provide insights into potential impacts, its speculative nature, due to the reliance on hypothetical assumptions rather than actual data, makes it less reliable, particularly in legal or dispute resolution contexts. Courts and tribunals are often hesitant to accept this method as it lacks concrete evidence and relies on assumptions that cannot be independently verified. Therefore, the IAP method should only be employed when no as-built data is available or it is not practicable to create as-built data retrospectively and other methods are not feasible.

In contrast, the choice of delay analysis methodology should be made based on a thorough consideration of the project's specific needs and constraints. When there is adequate time, budget, and access to comprehensive records, more detailed methods such as WA or TIA should be prioritized for their robustness. In contrast, when time is of the essence, methods such as APAB or CAB offer comparatively more cost-effective yet still valuable alternative. IAP method should only be used when no other options are viable and there is a clear lack of as-built data. The selected methodology should not only be technically appropriate but should also fit the project context, ensuring that the analysis is both credible and well-supported by the available evidence.

The following flowchart (Figure 1) has been prepared to outline, in general terms, a decision-making path that may assist in identifying a delay analysis methodology suited to the specific context of a construction project. It is important to emphasize that the diagram is not intended to prescribe or promote any particular method. Rather, it seeks to highlight the key criteria that practitioners may wish to consider when evaluating the suitability of various approaches. While the ultimate choice of methodology remains at the discretion of the project team or the

analyst, taking these factors into account is likely to enhance the appropriateness and defensibility of the selected method.

Figure 1 - Delay Analysis Method Selection Flowchart

3. CONCLUSION

This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of delay analysis methodologies and the fundamental definitions commonly used in the construction industry. By examining various approaches to delay analysis, their applicability, and the insights drawn from both academic literature and professional practice, this study aims to offer a practical perspective for those involved in addressing delay-related claims.

This study does not attempt to prescribe definitive solutions but instead provides an overview that aims to support informed decision making in the selection and application of delay analysis methods. By clarifying key considerations in this area, this work aims to contribute to a more accurate and balanced approach to handling delay related issues within the construction industry.

In particular, the study highlights five major delay analysis methodologies that are most prominently utilized within the construction industry, these are Impacted As-Planned, As-Planned vs. As-Built, Collapsed As-Built, Window Analysis, and Time Impact Analysis. Each method has distinct characteristics, advantages, and limitations, making it more or less suitable depending on the project context. In order to assist practitioners in selecting the most appropriate method, a set of selection criteria has been outlined, including factors such as data availability, project complexity, contract requirements, and the timing of the analysis. A simplified flow diagram is also presented to guide decision-making by offering a structured approach to the evaluation and selection of delay analysis methodologies.

While the discussed methodologies are widely recognized, their effectiveness often depends on the specific context of a project, such as the type, size, value, the skill level of the practitioner, and the contractual framework. It is essential for stakeholders to carefully evaluate these methods in light of their project's unique circumstances and ensure that the chosen methodology is aligned with both the contract terms (if applicable) and the project's specific needs.

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